

DEVELOPMENT OF A PROGRAM FOR CREATING EXPORTABLE FURNITURE PRODUCTS

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Abstract. *In this article, international trade entities are considered to propose principles that allow effective export product policy, effective formation and implementation of export product assortment, sales in the international market, and advertising activities.*

Keywords: *Enterprise, goods, products, export, market, sale, program.*

РАЗРАБОТКА ПРОГРАММЫ СОЗДАНИЯ ЭКСПОРТНОЙ МЕБЕЛЬНОЙ ПРОДУКЦИИ

Аннотация. *В данной статье субъектам международной торговли предлагается предложить принципы, позволяющие проводить эффективную экспортную товарную политику, эффективное формирование и реализацию экспортного товарного ассортимента, продажи на международном рынке, рекламную деятельность.*

Ключевые слова: *Предприятие, товары, продукция, экспорт, рынок, сбыт, программа.*

INTRODUCTION

Export is a source of effective development for the economy of Uzbekistan. Production and sale of goods and services to other countries is an important step in the development of our country and the growth of lifestyle. Export is a source of benefits for Uzbek enterprises and companies, their customers and employees of our society in general. Foreign market access is a source for manufacturers to introduce more competitive products and services to international markets. Also, constant pressure from competitors encourages us to invest, innovate and increase production. Therefore, the development of export activity is the main factor affecting the growth of the country's economic development.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Increasing the export potential of Gulobod Mebel LLC is related to the creation of products and collections suitable for the foreign market. The enterprise does not have the opportunity to locate production facilities abroad, so it can only use export-import operations.

International trade covers export-import operations, and these operations include activities related to:

- a) sale and export of goods abroad for the purpose of transfer to a foreign counterparty;
- b) buying goods from abroad and bringing them into the country in order to sell them in the domestic market.

Thus, the export of goods is the sale and export of goods to a foreign counterparty, while the import of goods is the purchase of goods from a foreign counterparty and its import into the country.

International trade implies that export-import operations are carried out on a commercial basis, that is, on the basis of conclusion and execution of sales contracts. Free goods delivery, service, work and assistance are considered separately and are not included in the export or import value.

The following marketing studies of an international nature should be carried out in the implementation of export goods policy for "Gulobod Mebel" LLC:

Studying the situation of the international market of these goods or services, identifying potential partner or competitor enterprises in the market of these goods and analyzing their working methods. Determining the methods of expanding or narrowing the range of export goods. To study the socio-cultural environment of the target section of the international market (level of national identity awareness, religious characteristics, distribution of social roles among members of society, language, gestures and customs).

Determination of rational and expedient forms of export (establishing direct relations with consumers, focus on joint activities, use of a network of foreign intermediaries).

State regulation and control of international trade activities of enterprises and organizations in foreign countries is carried out through licensing of export-import operations. Special (main and individual) permits are provided by state bodies corresponding to these types of activities.

A basic license is a special permit given to a market entity to export or import certain goods for a certain period of time, specifying the country in unlimited quantities. An individual license is a one-time special permit issued to a market entity to export or import certain goods for a limited period of time, specifying the country in a limited amount.

RESULTS

Licensing is a practical tool of international regulation of foreign trade relations, limiting the export of products necessary for domestic consumption, limiting imports in order to prevent damage to local producers, regulating the country's balance of trade and payments, temporary difficulties in the economy due to force majeure. It is widely used for purposes such as elimination, control of spending of foreign currency.

International trade entities try to conduct effective export goods policy. It proposes a certain course of action, principles that allow effective formation and implementation of the export product range as a result of following them. By its very nature, goods determine the fate of exports, therefore, all measures - creation, preparation, sale of goods on the international market, advertising, etc., occupy a central place in the export policy. Commercial success can only be achieved by products created after analyzing the market requirements of the country where the product is intended to be delivered. First of all, it is necessary to include the highest technical and economic specifications for the goods intended for export. Products intended for the domestic consumer and successful in the country may not be accepted abroad.

In export goods policy, the consumption value of goods is higher if they meet the requirements of foreign consumers according to their indicators. It is necessary to design the product to a predetermined, expected target group of buyers in the importing country, that is, not to the "average statistical buyer", but to specific buyers.

In international trade, three options of export goods policy are used.

1. The centralized option is directed to the creation and production of a new product in the foreign market that is technically and technologically similar to and compatible with the existing product of this manufacturer, designed to attract new foreign buyers. Creating a new product based on the direction of production of "Gulobod Mebel" LLC is not difficult from a technical point of view. But the complicated part is related to the creative ideas of designers and the correct understanding of the demand of foreign buyers.

2. Horizontal option. In this case, the new product of this manufacturer, released to the foreign market, is similar to the previously existing product and is aimed at a newly formed group of consumers, and its production is carried out with minor technological changes. Today, as indicated above, according to the criterion of financial possibilities of Gulobod Mebel LLC, this option is the most convenient. The range of goods established in the local market can be offered abroad. For example, bedroom collections can be offered to Kazakhstan without making any changes. It can be much cheaper and more affordable than a new product

3. Conglomerate option. In this case, a new product is introduced to the foreign market, which is not at all similar to the previously existing product of this manufacturer, which requires improvement of production technology and capture of a new market.

In the export goods policy of "Gulobod Mebel" LLC, various regulatory documents (international and national standards, customs requirements, etc.) valid in importing countries are applied, which affects the packaging, marking, design, some descriptions and documents of these goods. The product exporter must have a clear idea of his rights and obligations, scientific-technical, production and sales resources. It is important to strictly consider international trade methods and principles, which in many cases differ significantly from domestic methods and principles. In addition, it is permissible to take into account the features of registration and implementation of trade transactions, customs regulation, currency control, trade practices and customs in force in the country.

World experience shows that the availability of a variety of competitive export goods causes the response of the commercial world to increase the import of high-quality goods and the flow of foreign investments.

Most of the products sold in stores and markets today, from simple children's toys to expensive custom aircraft parts, are marked with special barcodes. Barcodes are a source of information that provides primary information about the product for both domestic and international markets. Attaching a barcode to a product means marking it with an identification number. The barcode system of the Republic of Uzbekistan is developed and operates within the framework of the EAN international commodity numbering system, ensures compatibility of national and international coding systems and a single language for information exchange.

Commodity policy in the international market is aimed at planning and implementation of a set of measures, which include innovation, modernization of existing goods in the market, elimination of goods from the production program of the enterprise working for the international market. In marketing, anything that can be consumed or bought to satisfy a need is called a commodity. A product unit is a whole, a whole that is different from others, and is characterized by indicators such as price, appearance and size. There are five different levels of goods: target goods - the basis of the concept of the goods, that is, the essence of the goods, the benefits derived from them. nature of the product - level of quality, set of features, distinctive features, brand name and distinctive packaging.

Expected goods - characteristics that the buyer intends to find in the purchased goods.

Reinforced goods - provision of additional services - delivery of goods to the buyer's home, installation, free replacement of damaged goods, etc. potential goods - new, original materials or unexpected, exclusive, design decisions.

The main marketing characteristics that accompany a product in the international market are product quality, assortment, packaging and design, branding and service policy. Product

description is determined in two directions - according to the technical characteristics of the product (non-stop operation, safety, ecological indicators) and according to the ability to satisfy the needs of the consumer. Therefore, product quality descriptions are divided into objective (technical) and subjective (convenience, fashion, and usage) types.

Upward expansion of the product range occurs when a company operating in the lower segment of the market seeks to occupy a position in the upper segment (spreads its activities in the upper segments of the market). The following are the main reasons for this: high growth rate, large profits in this part of the market, showing oneself as a manufacturer of a new product line; the possibility of increasing the reputation of existing goods. The main problems are as follows: competitors in the upper segment may attack and conquer the lower segments; customers do not believe that a company striving for a high segment can produce high-quality products; lack of necessary knowledge and experience in the company's sales representatives and distributors serving high segments.

Two-way expansion of the product range implies simultaneous expansion of the product range both upwards and downwards, that is, in both directions. An example of this is the activity of Sony.

DISCUSSION

Enrichment and renewal of the product range is due to the addition of new products. There are a number of reasons to enrich the product range: the desire to get additional profit; use of excess production capacity; trying to become a leading company rich in assortment; to compensate for shortcomings in the product range in order to repel the attacks of competitors. At the same time, saturating the assortment of goods can cause some goods to be "eaten" by other goods and confuse the buyer. It follows that the company needs to make sure that the new product is sufficiently different from the existing product. In some cases, it will be enough to slightly modernize the quality of existing goods, for example, to revise the design of goods.

Assortment policy. Determining the composition and number of goods and services delivered to the foreign market is important in international assortment policy. Product line assortment decisions in turn determine the company's production program. The basis of the assortment policy is the segmentation of consumers in the foreign market, as a result of which the company makes a decision in favor of an assortment policy focused on the target group of consumers and (or) countries.

At the international level, the assortment policy of companies is influenced by two main groups - internal and external group factors.

External factors include legal restrictions on the supply of goods, the level of competition, the development of sales channels, the socio-cultural characteristics of consumers, and the following elements: program content (volume), "width and height" of the program, the direction of the program and the policy of the portfolio.

The content of the program is determined by the number of products in the product range. The main problem in determining the product program is to determine the "independent" units (product and modifications) in the product group.

CONCLUSION

The "width and height" of the program is determined by the number of product groups offered to the foreign market and the number of options within each group, respectively.

The orientation of the product program is the orientation of the assortment to the product description, target consumer group, price, and so on.

The portfolio policy depends on the direction of the product policy, which determines the compatibility of the previous three elements of the product program with the company's strategic tasks in the foreign market.

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